

Family Lamiaceae : phytoremediation aspects

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Abstract : In a pot experiment, saplings of *Ocimum basilicum*, *O. sanctum*, *O. americanum* and *Mentha spicata* were planted in metal amended soils. The plants of *O. sanctum* and *O. americanum* were unable to survive after 120 days. The aerial parts of *O. basilicum* were harvested after 120 and 210 days while *Mentha* after 90, 150 and 210 days. They were subjected to steam distillation and extracted with *n*-hexane and dichloromethane. The oil composition was analyzed by GC and GC/MS. Metal (copper and lead) content was determined by atomic absorption spectroscopy. There was significant quantitative variation in the composition of essential oil for *O. basilicum* growing on copper amended soil as compared to lead amended soils while no change was observed for *M. spicata*. Both, *O. basilicum* and *M. spicata* showed vigorous growth with no symptoms of morpho-phytotoxicity, despite the accumulation of lead and copper. *O. basilicum* showed better metal accumulation than *M. spicata*.

Keywords : *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha spicata*, essential oil, copper, lead.

Introduction

The cleanup of contaminated soils by phytoremediation measures is emerging as an environment friendly technique. Metal contaminated soil can be remediated by chemical, physical and biological techniques. Sources of anthropogenic metal contamination include smelting of metalliferous ores, electroplating, gas exhaust, energy and fuel production, the application of fertilizers and municipal sludges to land and industrialization^{1,2}. The importance of biodiversity is increasingly being considered for the clean up of metal contaminated and polluted systems³. Studies have been conducted on phytoaccumulation by using aromatic and medicinal crops⁴⁻⁷. The contamination of agricultural soils by heavy metals is well documented^{8,9}. There are reports on the effect in Japanese mint, peppermint, basil and dill oil constituents following metal treatments^{4,5,10-12}. The effects of Cd, Pb and Cu on the growth and essential oil contents in dill, peppermint and basil has been studied by Valtcho *et al.*^{13,14}.

Ocimum and *Mentha* species are widely cultivated in India for their aroma chemicals. To the best of our knowledge, there is no report on phytoremediation measures using *Ocimum* and *Mentha* species from Uttarakhand. Therefore, in this study, pot experiments have been conducted to investigate phytoremediation capacities of *O. basilicum*, *O. sanctum*, *O. americanum* and *M. spicata*.

Results and discussion

The main physicochemical characteristics of control soil are listed in Table 1. The pH was near neutral (7.64) with EC value of 0.146 dS m⁻¹ and organic carbon 4.710%. The soil texture was loam with CEC of 26.16 cmol_c kg⁻¹. The total lead and copper content was 27.442 and 1.325 mg kg⁻¹ respectively while DTPA extractable Pb and copper was 0.345 and 0.263 mg kg⁻¹ respectively. Total and DTPA extractable lead and copper concentrations in soil at each cutting are shown in Table 2. The total and DTPA extractable metal content significantly decrease ($p \leq 0.5$) with the time of cutting. After 120 days, it was observed that *O. sanctum* and *O.*

Table 1. Soil properties

Physical properties	Control soil
pH (1 : 2)	7.64 ± 0.045
EC (1 : 2) (dS m ⁻¹)	0.146 ± 0.006
Organic carbon (%)	4.710 ± 0.209
CEC (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	26.16 ± 0.299
Total Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	27.442 ± 0.414
Total Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)	1.325 ± 0.119
Available Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.345 ± 0.041
Available Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.263 ± 0.033
Soil texture	Loam

Values are mean ± standard deviations of four replicates.

Table 2. Concentration of total and DTPA extractable Pb and Cu in treated soils and in plants (mg kg⁻¹)

Metal concentration		<i>O. basilicum</i>						<i>M. spicata</i>					
		Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)			Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)			Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)			Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)		
		DTPA			DTPA			DTPA			DTPA		
		Total	extractable	Plant	Total	extractable	Plant	Total	extractable	Plant	Total	extractable	Plant
Cutting I	0	11.925a	2.266a	0.500a	8.250a	1.570a	0.220a	27.250a	2.380a	0.870a	12.527a	5.178a	0.116a
	1	300.500c	60.100c	31.167b	190.155c	38.033c	39.600b	201.150c	35.318d	14.350c	185.886d	38.219d	2.609b
	2	373.800e	71.022e	42.200d	220.172e	41.835d	47.333c	277.997e	48.072e	19.833d	282.778h	47.260f	2.685b
	3	435.795g	78.443f	47.200e	391.117g	70.402f	51.867d	465.060g	66.986h	27.000f,g	352.559j	88.362k	4.511d
	4	504.815i	95.915h	52.217f	432.026h	82.088h	58.867f	474.977h	81.782i	28.333g	452.341i	85.496j	6.673e
Cutting II	0	10.000a	1.900a	0.760a	7.900a	1.500a	0.300a	22.340a	2.375a	2.200a,b	12.498a	4.245a	0.237a
	1	278.000b	52.820b	34.350c	181.167b	36.234b	45.000c	195.308c	32.449b	15.410c	170.785c	37.109d	3.621c
	2	350.000d	66.567d	50.400f	202.200d	38.418c	54.200e	250.264d	33.252c	24.217e	195.601e	42.545e	4.463d
	3	400.000f	68.000d	60.000g	347.950f	62.630e	77.950g	455.240g	50.041d	25.213e,f	263.374g	86.496j,k	7.326f
	4	457.000h	82.260g	78.366h	392.217g	74.520g	82.217h	460.415g	64.921g	26.323e,f,g	360.671k	82.876i	12.326g
Cutting III	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	19.113a	2.154a	4.317b	11.34a	3.632a	0.418a
	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	154.050b	30.498b	42.248h	160.516b	29.270b	4.329d
	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	201.157c	32.059b	57.179i	188.587d	34.197c	4.621d
	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	399.486f	46.471e	70.580j	244.585f	75.902h	19.284h
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	405.378f	54.117f	81.496k	300.648i	72.968g	30.435i

0 = control, 1 = 500 mg kg⁻¹ for Pb and 270 mg kg⁻¹ for Cu, 2 = 600 mg kg⁻¹ for Pb and 300 mg kg⁻¹ for Cu, 3 = 750 mg kg⁻¹ for Pb and 500 mg kg⁻¹ for Cu, 4 = 900 mg kg⁻¹ for Pb and 700 mg kg⁻¹ for Cu.

Mean values within columns followed by different letters (a-l) are significantly different at the level of $P < 0.05$ according to the Duncan test.

americanum were unable to survive.

The results indicated that after 90 days of treatment, permissible concentration (m'_{270}) for copper (31.88 g) and m'_{600} for lead (39.53 g) shown the highest dry mass production of *M. spicata*. After 120 days, maximum biomass production was observed in m'_{270} (copper) and m'_{500} (lead) treatments for both the tested plants. After 210 days, in *O. basilicum*, copper addition at 270 mg kg⁻¹ concentration resulted in the highest biomass production (53 g) while in case of lead, the highest dry weight was observed in unamended soil (46.63 g). In *Mentha*, the highest biomass production was noted in the second treatment of copper and lead (permissible concentration). The results also suggested that the highest dry mass production was observed in 120 days of treatments in both the plants which may affect the oil yield of these tested plants. Heavy metal pollution resulted in 5 to 72% dry mass inhibition in *O. basilicum* while *Mentha spicata* results in reduction of 4.5 to 75% dry mass reduction in the different treated soils (Figs. 1–4). Reduction of dry mass was observed more in copper amended soils as compared to lead amended soils. Previous results have revealed that elevated concentrations of Cd, Pb and Cu in growth me-

Fig. 1. Effect of Cu on dry weight of *Ocimum basilicum*.

dium have led to the reduction in the yields in plants^{6,11,12}. In our study, both the metals reduced dry yield of tested plants. The similar results were reported by many scientists in other crops^{9,13,15}. It is reported that elevated heavy metal concentration in the soil can lead to enhanced up take by the plant and have a negative effect on plant growth¹⁶. At higher concentrations they interfere with metabolic processes and inhibit growth, sometimes leading to plant death, as was the case seen in *O. sanctum* and

Fig. 2. Effect of Pb on dry weight of *Ocimum basilicum*.

Fig. 3. Effect of Cu on dry weight of *Mentha spicata*.

Fig. 4. Effect of Pb on dry weight of *Mentha spicata*.

O. americanun. The plants of *O. basilicum* are tolerant to both lead and copper at 900 and 700 mg kg⁻¹ respectively as they showed vigorous growth with no symptoms of

morphotoxicity. Schnoor (1997)¹⁷ reported that any plant useful for phytoremediation should be vigorously growing, easily harvestable and exhibit a biomass of more than three tons DW (dry weight) per hectare. These observations are yet to be assessed by conducting field trials.

Effect of addition of lead and copper on metal concentrations in plants and soil has been shown in Table 2. The availability of lead in soil depends upon soil pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC), organic carbon content; soil/water Eh (redox potential) and phosphate levels. Very few plants have been identified to have the potential to uptake lead¹⁸. In *Ocimum*, the highest mean concentration of Pb extracted from the soil, 78.366 mg kg⁻¹ was in the pots which had the maximum amount of lead salt (900 mg kg⁻¹) after 210 days while the lowest mean concentration of lead was present in the unamended control (0.500 mg kg⁻¹). Zheljzakov *et al.* (2008)¹⁴ have reported the presence of 248.0 and 123.2 mg kg⁻¹ of lead in aerial basil tissue by watering the plants once a week with 500 mg L⁻¹ lead till harvesting. Zheljzakov *et al.* (2006)¹⁴ observed that Pb accumulation in the stem and leaves of basil was 41 and 27.5 mg kg⁻¹ in 100 mg L⁻¹ Pb amended soils. In all soils, added lead significantly increased metal concentration in plants as compared to the control. The concentration of DTPA extractable lead in all treated soils significantly. Phytoextraction of Pb by the plant can be seen by decrease in the percentage of DTPA extractable Pb (Table 2).

The highest mean concentration of copper extracted from the soil 82.217 mg kg⁻¹ was in the pots which had the maximum quantity of added copper (700 mg kg⁻¹) in the second cutting. Zheljzakov *et al.* (2008)¹⁴ have reported the presence of 84.7 and 63.4 mg kg⁻¹ of copper in aerial basil tissue by watering the plants once a week with 150 mg L⁻¹ copper till harvesting. Copper addition (100 mg L⁻¹) significantly increased the concentration in stem (24.1 mg kg⁻¹) and leaves (22.5 mg kg⁻¹) of basil as compared to the control (Zheljzakov *et al.*, 2006)¹³. The lowest mean concentration of copper was present in the unamended control (0.220 ppm). In all soils, added copper significantly increased metal concentration in plants in comparison to the control. DTPA extractable Cu significantly decreased from cutting I to cutting II (Table 2). Linalool content of *O. basilicum* significantly increased

while methyl chavicol decreased in both copper and lead amended soils.

In *Mentha*, the highest mean concentration of lead extracted from the soil ($81.496 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) was in the pots having highest concentration of added metal (900 mg kg^{-1}). The presence of 81.3 and 278.0 mg kg^{-1} of lead in aerial peppermint tissue was reported by watering the plants once a week with 500 mg L^{-1} lead till harvesting¹⁴. Lead accumulation in the stem and leaves of peppermint was 17.2 and 28.0 mg kg^{-1} respectively in 100 mg L^{-1} Pb amended soils¹³. The lowest mean concentration of copper was present in the unamended control *M. spicata* (0.870 mg kg^{-1}). It was observed that the DTPA extractable metal concentration significantly decreased (Table 2) from the first to the third cutting which is reflected by the significant increase in metal concentration in plants.

The highest mean concentration of copper extracted by *Mentha* from the soil ($30.435 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) was in the pots which had the maximum quantity of added salt 700 mg kg^{-1} in the third cutting. The presence of $36.5.0$ and 31.8 mg kg^{-1} of lead in aerial peppermint tissue was reported by watering the plants once a week with 150 mg L^{-1} lead till harvesting¹⁴. Copper accumulation in the peppermint stem (27.2 mg kg^{-1}) and leave (44.9 mg kg^{-1}) tissue increased as compared to the control by the addition of 100 mg L^{-1} copper in soil¹³. The lowest mean concentration of copper was present in the unamended control *M. spicata* (0.116 mg kg^{-1}). DTPA extractable copper concentration in soil decreased significantly with significant increase in metal concentration in plant.

Permissible limit for copper in the soil in India is $135\text{--}270 \text{ ppm}$ ¹⁹. It is reported that elevated heavy metal concentrations in the soil can lead to enhanced up take by the plant and have a negative effect on plant growth¹⁶. At higher concentrations they interfere with metabolic processes and inhibit growth, sometimes leading to plant death. *M. spicata* is capable to tolerate 700 mg kg^{-1} copper concentration added to soil. The plants have grown vigorously with no toxicity symptoms in all Cu amended soils.

The permissible limit of lead in the soil in India is $250\text{--}500 \text{ ppm}$ ¹⁹ while the range in uncontaminated soils in India is $3\text{--}200 \text{ ppm}$ ²⁰. It has been reported that addition of chelating agents such as EDTA to the soil increase

the uptake of heavy metals by the plant²¹. Therefore, the addition of a chelating reagents should further increases the phytoremediation capacity of the plant. The range of copper and lead in uncontaminated soil is $2\text{--}100 \text{ ppm}$ and $2\text{--}200 \text{ ppm}$ ^{19,20}. The level of lead (10 mg kg^{-1}) and copper (100 mg kg^{-1}) in the plant is above the permissible limit. A field study of Pb phytoextraction has been reported by various scented *Pelargonium* cultivars²².

Transfer factor (TF) of copper was higher as compared to lead irrespective of the plant species (Figs. 5–8). TF increases with the time of cutting in both the tested plants. TF of lead was higher for *O. basilicum* as compared to *Mentha* while the reverse was true for copper.

Fig. 5. Transfer factor of Cu in *O. basilicum*.

Fig. 6. Transfer factor of Pb in *O. basilicum*.

Experimental

Plant material :

The saplings of *O. basilicum*, *O. sanctum*, *O. americanum* and *M. spicata* were purchased from MRDC,

Fig. 7. Transfer factor of Cu in *M. spicata*.

Fig. 8. Transfer factor of Pb in *M. spicata*.

Pantnagar and planted in pots (four replicates). The botanical identification of the specimens was done at Botany Department, Kumaun University, Nainital and Botanical Survey of India, Dehradun.

Preparation of soil samples :

Surface (0–15 cm) soil sample was collected from a field of Rudrapur. The soil samples were prepared for physicochemical analysis. These samples were air-dried, ground into fine powder using pestle and mortar and passed through a 2 mm sieve.

Soil characteristics :

Five kilogram of the soil was filled in the pots. The inorganic salts of heavy metal sources were added to the soils to provide lead (0, 500 (*m'*) 600, 750, 900 mg kg⁻¹) and copper (0, 270 (*m'*) 300, 500, 700 mg kg⁻¹) concentration of the metals. A basal dose of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O at

the rate of 30, 20, 30 mg kg⁻¹ respectively was applied to all the pots and mixed with the soil. After treatments, soil of each pot was thoroughly mixed on a polythene sheet and transferred to plastic pots (40). Hence, the pot experiment receiving a combination of 2 metals, 5 heavy metal concentrations and 4 replicates in the completely randomized design set up. After 90, 120, 150 and 210 days of plantation, the processed soil samples were used for determining their physicochemical properties pH, EC²³, texture, % organic carbon²⁴, CEC²⁵ and metals.

Preparation of plant samples for heavy metal analysis :

The aerial parts of *Ocimum* were harvested after 120 and 210 days while *Mentha* after 90, 150 and 210 days. The plant samples were thoroughly washed to remove all adhered soil particles. Samples were cut into small pieces, air dried for 2 days and finally dried at 100±1 °C in a hot air oven for 3 h. The samples were ground in warm condition and passed through 2 mm sieve. Dry plant tissue was finely ground wet-ashed using HNO₃ : H₂SO₄ : HClO₄ (10 : 1 : 4 v/v)²⁶.

Preparation of soil samples for heavy metal analysis :

Well mixed samples of 2 g each were taken in 250 ml glass beakers and digested with 8 ml of aqua regia on a sand bath for 2 h. After evaporation to near dryness, the samples were dissolved with 10 ml of 2% nitric acid, filtered and then diluted to 50 ml with distilled water²⁷. Soil samples were extracted for DTPA extractable heavy metals following the procedure developed by Lindsay and Norvell²⁸.

Heavy metal analysis :

Lead (Pb) and copper (Cu) and analysis in soil and plant (on dry weight basis) samples were performed on an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (GBC-902 Avanta Sigma Model, Australia) using acetylene gas as fuel and air as an oxidizer. Mean values of four replicates were taken for each determination. The transfer factor (TF) which is found to be the ability of plant to transfer heavy metals from the roots to the harvestable aerial parts²⁸. It was calculated on a dry weight basis by using the formula :

$$TF = \frac{\text{metal concentration in shoot mg kg}^{-1}}{\text{metal concentration in root mg kg}^{-1}}$$

Statistical analysis :

The data were analyzed using variance analysis (ANOVA) SPSS 16.0 statistical software and the results were calculated by with four replications. The statistical significance was tested at probability level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates the ability of *O. basilicum* and *M. spicata* to tolerate high concentrations of lead and copper in the pot experiments, encouraging the farmers to take up the cultivation of these species for commercial purpose as a green method in heavy metal polluted sites. The increase in the concentration of linalool in *O. basilicum* also enhances the quality of essential oil. With the increasing vehicular traffic and rapid industrialization, the growing of aromatic crops in the vicinity of these contaminated sites is a preferable option rather than the cultivation of food crops which are proving to be a source of heavy metals in the food chain.

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